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Fam234b is selectively activated during the first cell division of the human embryo.

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We studied gene expression in the human embryo immediately after fertilization and zygotic activation and at the first cell division from 1-cell to 2-cell stage. We describe here discovery/identification of Fam234b as a zygotic cell factor required or important during the first cell division of the fertilized human embryo.